

Degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence and related with Job Performance

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to ascertain the Degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence and related with Job Performance. The study population was identified as 179 mathematics teachers who teach mathematics in government schools affiliated with the Bani Ubaid Education Directorate in Irbid Governorate - Jordan. The study sample consisted of 138 mathematics teachers who were selected by a simple random method. The study used descriptive statistics method. The researcher designed a questionnaire consisting of 20 items to measure the degree of possession mathematics teachers to emotional intelligence, and another questionnaire consisting of 20 items to measure the job performance of mathematics teachers. The results showed that the degree of mathematics teachers' possession of emotional intelligence is high, and there is a positive and strong relationship between emotional intelligence and the job performance of mathematics teachers.

KEYWORDS: Degree of possession, Emotionally Intelligent, Job Performance, Mathematics Teachers.

INTRODUCTION

The learning process at school is complex and comprehensive. Many people argue that to achieve high achievement in learning, a person must have high intelligence because intelligence is the provision of potential that will facilitate learning and in turn, will produce optimal learning achievement. But the phenomenon shows that not a few people with high intelligence have a low achievement, and there are many people with moderate intelligence who can surpass the learning achievements of high intelligence people. This shows that intelligence cannot always predict one's learning achievement, especially in problem-solving abilities. There are other important factors, namely emotional intelligence (Maryani et al ,2019).

Emotional Intelligence (EI) generally has the same meaning from some experts, namely the ability or skill of a person to recognize and respond to emotions appropriately, motivate, empathize, and control oneself and others (Wood, 2020). According to Torndike (2015) emotional intelligence is the ability to understand others and act wisely in human relations.

Cherniss, (2006) determined the components of emotional intelligence may be divided into five basic pillars, according to what Goleman defined: 1) Self-awareness: This includes awareness of emotional expressions that appear on the face and tone of voice. 2) Self-management: It means controlling the conscience, and thus we ensure control over the actions. 3) Self-motivation means directing emotions to serve a goal and using them in a productive way to achieve achievement and excellence. 4) Empathy means knowing and understanding the feelings of others, which leads to emotional harmony with others. 5) Social communication is the management of emotions in dealing with others based on understanding and knowing their feelings.

Teacher is very important to have emotional intelligence for Knowing before starting learning because he determine the best method so that students can take lessons well (Slavin, 2010). Teacher performance can be influenced by internal and external factors, in this case instructional, transformational and spiritual leadership influences teacher performance (Nurabadi et al., 2021). teachers must participate in their teaching to implement emotionally intelligent learning (Pozo-Rico & Sandoval, 2020). The teacher's emotional intelligence and performance are significantly correlated, while the teacher's attitude is significantly correlated with teacher performance (Jimenez, 2020). Kuswanto, Malihah, Saerozi, and & Subqi (2023) asserted show that emotional intelligence and emotional sensitivity can shape teacher performance, teacher emotional intelligence has been proven to be a strong predictor in shaping teachers' attitude.

Without emotional intelligence, students cannot control, motivate, and control themselves and focus on learning even though these students can follow ongoing lessons, which results in low learning outcomes (Lolombulan, 2017). Karimah (2016) argues that emotional intelligence has an important role in achieving success, with low emotional intelligence will cause students difficulty in focusing (concentration) on during the teaching and learning process.

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Ibrahim, et al (2023) indicated There is a positive and significant relationship between emotional intelligence and student mathematics learning outcomes, and there is a relationship between emotional intelligence and self-efficacy with students' mathematics learning outcomes. Dafid et al (2020) found that there was a positive correlation between emotional intelligence in social interaction and mathematics achievement. Faradillahand Wulandari (2021) demonstrated that students who have high mathematical flexibility have high emotional intelligence. Ugwuanyi stated that there was a positive relationship between students' emotional intelligence and mathematics learning achievement (Ugwuanyi et al., 2020). Coesamin et al (2021) showed a significant relationship between students' emotional intelligence and students' mathematical representation abilities. Herut, Muleta, and Lebeta (2024) underscored the importance of EI in academic achievement and provide valuable insights for educational practitioners and parents.

Maryani et al (2019) obtained information about the influence of emotional intelligence on the ability of students' mathematical problem-solving. His research was conducted at Junior High School State for class eight students. The research is a quantitative survey research with descriptive analysis method. The data obtained is data from the retrieval of the questionnaire then analyzed the results. The results showed that there was an influence of emotional intelligence on students' mathematical problem-solving abilities. Shafiee et al (2016) investigated the relationship between emotional intelligence to deal with math scores. Their search on female students in secondary schools of area 1 in Rey selected randomly in relative cluster. The sample consisted of 120 female students of mathematics in high schools of Rey that 60 students in the experimental group and 60 students in the control group aged 15 to 18 were selected. The experimental group, with a mean average of three years of math under 14 and the control group, with a mean average of three years of math top of 14. In this study, the emotional questionnaire of shot was used and the result was evaluated by t test. The results of the analysis showed that between emotional intelligence and math scores, there is a significant difference.

Previous literature has been interested in investigating the role of mathematics teachers' emotional intelligence in their mathematics teaching. Gizem and Bilge determined that teachers had high levels of teaching style, self-efficacy, and emotional intelligence. A positive and moderate correlation was found between teachers' teaching styles and self-efficacy levels, teaching styles and emotional intelligence levels, and emotional intelligence levels and self-efficacy. senel et al (2014) revealed relationships between teachers' emotional intelligence, general self-efficacy, and teaching self- efficacy beliefs. Hunter (2021) revealed that emotional intelligence substantially influences job satisfaction, trust, and success. Cakirpaloglu et al (2023) aimed to determine whether there is a relationship between prosocial tendencies and the level of emotional intelligence in a sample of teachers. The research group consisted of 997 primary and secondary school teachers, of whom 109 were men and 889 women. The correlation coefficient calculation shows a significant negative relationship between the level of emotional intelligence and age, and the length of work experience.

Kassim, Bambale, & Jakada (2016) conducted a study that sought to Knowing the relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction in universities within Kano State. The study sample consisted of 2,502 lecturers from all universities in Kano State, using a convenient sampling method. The study used the analytical approach. The study adopted the Wong scale to measure emotional intelligence, and the McDonold and McInter scale to measure the extent of job satisfaction. The results of the analysis showed a statistically significant relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction, while emotional evaluations were found to have no relationship to job satisfaction.

Singh & Kumar (2016) also conducted a study that sought to determine the impact of emotional intelligence and gender on the job satisfaction of primary school teachers in America. A group of (333) male and female teachers in primary schools were randomly selected, and the study adopted the analytical approach. They found The study showed a significant positive relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction.

Through the results of Singh and Kumar (2016) study`s, it was shown that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction. Emotional intelligence is related to the ability to manage emotions to improve job performance and works to help teachers be calm and use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior properly to achieve goals. This skill promotes open and honest communication, leading to better collaboration and less downside. Teachers with high emotional intelligence are able to inspire and motivate their students, which results in increased student engagement and improved learning.

Begall et, al, (2020 445) defined job performance as “the employee’s desire to do challenging work, maintain the modernity of his skills, his desire to assume additional responsibilities, and his active participation in meetings”. Widyastuti et al, (2020) mentioned Job performance evaluation is an important factor in improving the quality of decisions related to human resources, such as: motivating and training employees to improve their ability to carry out job duties with high efficiency; Which contributes to improving organizational performance as a whole.

Egboka & Alike (2018) conducted a study in Nigeria that aimed to determine the level of job performance among secondary school teachers. The study sample consisted of (665) male and female teachers who were randomly selected. The questionnaire was used as a tool for collecting data. The results of the study indicated The level of job performance among secondary school teachers was medium.

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Based on the aforementioned importance of mathematics teachers possessing emotional intelligence, and the existence of a relationship between it and job performance, the study therefore sought to verify the degree to which mathematics teachers in Jordan possess emotional intelligence, and to determine the highest levels that mathematics teachers possess. In addition to studying the existence of a relationship between emotional intelligence and their job performance as mathematics teachers.

Significance of the Study

The importance of this study lies in the role of emotional intelligence in the teaching process, and the importance of teachers in general and mathematics teachers in particular possessing emotional intelligence skills, which is reflected in their job performance in teaching. The results of the study show that mathematics teachers possess emotional intelligence skills, highlighting the effectiveness of emotional intelligence in the process of teaching mathematics. There is a link between emotional intelligence and the performance of mathematics teachers in teaching mathematics effectively and efficiently. The importance of the study in providing mathematics teachers and academic researchers with measures (study instrument) may be useful in developing similar relevant measures.

Research Question

The study attempted to verify the answer to the following questions:

1. What is degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence?
2. What is the degree of job performance among mathematics teachers?
3. Is there relation between the degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence and Job Performance?

Study Delimitation

The study was delimited to all mathematics teachers that teaching mathematic at all government schools of the Directorate of Education, Bani Obaid region, Irbid Governorate, Jordan, who teach mathematic for basic stage in the academic year of 2023-2024. The study attempted to ascertain Degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence and related with Job Performance. The study was limited to the answers of mathematics teachers on study instruments.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher applied descriptive research in the field, as well as giving the study sample study materials, calculating the means and frequencies of the math teachers' responses, and helping to accurately and clearly determine the degree of possession. A quantitative data can be made available to all members of society, and the study's conclusions are highly reliable.

Study population and its sample

The study population is all math teachers who teach students in the basic stage of mathematics in the Bani Ubaid District Education Directorate in the Irbid Governorate for the academic year 2023–2024. Based on data from the directorate for the same year, the total number of math teachers was 179. The study sample, which included 138 teachers, was selected using the simple random sampling approach. This represents 78.8% of the study population. According to Abu Saleh and Awad (2012), the larger the sample, the more accurately it represents the community.

Study Instrumentation

The researcher developed the two questionnaire of the study in the light of the study literature, where the identification consisted of two parts, first: the degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence , and the number of paragraphs is (25) paragraph. second: the degree of job performance among mathematics teachers. and contained a paragraph (25). The questionnaire resolution was Likert Five Scale. The fifth level indicates that the degree is high, and the lower the teacher's answer. Closer to the first level, the degree is decreased. The arithmetic averages for the degree of inclusion were classified into five levels: very high, high, medium, little, and very little, according to the following equation:

(Highest value - minimum value) ÷ Number of levels.

$$\frac{5-1}{5} = \frac{4}{5} = 0.8$$

This value is equal to the length of the category, and therefore:

From 1.00-1.8 is very low From 1.81-2.6 a few From 2.61-3.4 medium
From 3.41-4.2 high From 4.21-5.00 is very high

Validity and Reliability

To ensure the veracity of the two questionnaire, the researcher presented the preliminary picture of it to a group of reviewer's with knowledge and experience in this field. The preliminary picture of the identification was 10 reviewers. The reviewer's' observations included a number of suggestions, such as redrafting some paragraphs, increasing the number of subparagraphs, clarifying some paragraphs, shortening some paragraphs, and the paragraph should be of a single and uncomplicated purpose, and suggesting that the paragraphs should be linked to mathematics teaching. Subsequently, an amended questionnaire was prepared in accordance with

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the previous reviewer's suggestions and was again submitted to four former arbitrators. Their suggestions were limited and few, and the final identification was prepared by the researcher on the basis of the suggestions and guidance of all arbitrators.

To extract the indicators of validity construction of the scale, the coefficients of each paragraph and between the overall grade, between each paragraph and its attachment to the area to which it belongs, and between the areas and the total degree, were extracted in a survey sample from outside the study sample consisting of (30) teachers, the correlation coefficients of the paragraphs with the tool as a whole ranged from (0.38-0.89) to (0.39-0.89). Correlation coefficients were (0.93) and (0.9) for each questionnaire in order, which are acceptable.

To ensure the reliability of the study tool, it was verified using the test-retest method by applying the scale, and re-applying it two weeks later to a group of (30) teachers outside the study sample, and then the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated between their estimates the two times. The reliability coefficients was (0.87) and (0.85). and internal consistency coefficients were (0.84) and (0.81) for each questionnaire in order, which are acceptable.

FINDING

The study presents its results, as the number of study questions was three, and they were answered through the questionnaire prepared for this study.

The first question: What is degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations were extracted for the degree to degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence, and the table (1) below shows this.

Table 1. Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence.

Rank	Number	Paragraphs	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Degree
1	1	I prepare well before the mathematics lesson, so that I can teach the students easily	3.69	.93	High
5	2	When I have difficulty explaining mathematical ideas, I start with the easy idea and then gradually move to the main idea	3.63	.88	High
20	3	I find it difficult to ask questions when I don't understand mathematics	3.36	.94	Medium
19	4	I sometimes find it difficult to explain mathematical subjects to students	3.38	.98	Medium
14	5	Find out quickly if students are having difficulty learning mathematics	3.56	.90	High
17	6	Using another method if students do not understand the method I use in teaching mathematics	3.44	.96	High
4	7	I can teach math even if I'm upset about something	3.65	.90	High
8	8	I easily control my anger when I study mathematics	3.60	.88	High
13	9	I answer students' questions before the mathematics exam	3.57	.87	High
15	10	I try to keep solving math problems until I get an answer	3.52	.96	High
2	11	I can provide answers to difficult mathematics questions	3.68	.91	High
6	12	When answering a difficult math question, I try to think of multiple solutions to solve it	3.63	.93	High
7	13	I appreciate the positive relationship between me and the students	3.63	.95	High
10	14	I always provide assistance to students	3.59	1.01	High
11	15	I take into account the students' personal and family circumstances	3.58	.94	High
15	16	I intervene in resolving conflicts between students and work to resolve them	3.55	1.02	High
12	17	My negative circumstances do not affect my teaching	3.57	1.01	High
3	18	I can summon positive emotions such as fun and humor easily.	3.66	.90	High
9	19	I avoid showing my feelings and reactions when angry.	3.60	.88	High
18	20	I can contain the feelings of stress that affect teaching mathematics	3.44	.96	High
Possession Emotional Intelligence			3.56	High	

It is clear from the table (1) that the degree of mathematics teachers' possession of emotional intelligence is high with a arithmetic mean (3.56). The highest levels were in the following order: First: "I prepare well before the mathematics lesson, so that I can teach the students easily", with a arithmetic mean (3.69). Second: "I can provide answers to difficult mathematics questions". with a arithmetic mean (3.68). Third: "I can summon positive emotions such as fun and humor easily". with a arithmetic mean (3.66).

The Second question: What is the degree of job performance among mathematics teachers?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations were extracted for the degree of job performance among mathematics teachers, and the table (2) below shows this.

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Table 2. Arithmetic means and standard deviations for the degree of job performance among mathematics teachers

Rank	Number	Paragraphs	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Degree
1	1	Create a suitable climate for teaching mathematics	3.95	.819	High
3	2	I provide administrative proposals and recommendations to the school administration	3.78	.743	High
5	3	Have the ability to make the right decisions at the right time	3.68	.601	High
6	4	Review the mathematics curricula and learning outcomes	3.69	.796	High
11	5	I complete my tasks accurately without needing extra time	3.60	.771	High
17	6	I deal with my colleagues with kindness and respect	3.44	.863	High
2	7	I motivate my colleagues to do their best in achieving the school's goals.	3.82	.742	High
4	8	I take into account the needs and capabilities of the school when planning school activities.	3.73	.761	High
19	9	I accept the administrative roles and tasks assigned to me by the school administration	3.40	.731	Medium
7	10	Respect your work and class schedules.	3.69	.827	High
10	11	Report any observations that require appropriate action to the school administration	3.66	.620	High
12	12	I don't mind undertaking tasks in addition to my current tasks.	3.57	.790	Medium
13	13	Solve some simple administrative problems that do not require intervention from the school administration	3.57	.844	High
14	14	I strive to continuously improve my teaching performance	3.57	.835	High
8	15	Participate in qualification and development courses without hesitation	3.69	1.010	High
16	16	I monitor students' mathematics education on an ongoing basis	3.52	.883	High
20	17	Using various teaching strategies to teach mathematics	3.36	.830	Medium
18	18	Using various assessment strategies to teach mathematics	3.44	.991	High
9	19	Implement instructions and laws issued by educational authorities without disturbance	3.69	.845	High
15	20	I participate in outdoor activities constantly	3.57	.744	High
Job Performance			3.62	High	

It is clear from the table (2) that the degree of mathematics teachers' Job Performance is high with a arithmetic mean (3.62).

The Third question: Is there relation between the degree of possession mathematics teachers in Jordan to emotional intelligence and Job Performance?

To answer this question, the Pearson correlation coefficient was extracted to show the relationship between the Possession of emotional intelligence among mathematics teachers in Jordan and their job performance, and table (3) explained:

Table 3. Pearson correlation coefficient between the Possession of emotional intelligence and job performance

		Emotional intelligence	Job Performance
Emotional intelligence	Numbers	138	138
	Pearson Correlation	1	0.856
	Sig		0.000
Job Performance	Numbers	138	138
	Pearson Correlation	0.856	1
	Sig	0.000	

It is clear from Table (3) that there is a statistically significant correlation at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the Possession of emotional intelligence among mathematics teachers and their job performance, where the value of the correlation between emotional intelligence and job performance reached (0.856).

DISCUSSIONS

The first question

The results showed that the degree the Possession of emotional intelligence mathematics teachers in Jordan is high. This indicates the interest of mathematics teachers in possessing emotional intelligence and their belief in the importance of emotional intelligence in teaching mathematics. This helps them create effective learning environments. They are able to motivate their students by understanding their behavioral and psychological state. These teachers are sensitive to their students' disturbing behaviors, pay close attention to their academic performance, and are skilled at managing relationships. The teacher can instill self-awareness in students by creating a classroom atmosphere that encourages thinking and discovery, which encourages them to discuss, choose their favorite side, and read the emotions of others during the discussion.

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Teachers who have emotional intelligence skills are characterized by high self-confidence and the ability to solve problems and innovate solutions. They can also deal with difficult situations effectively, and they are respected by their principals and schoolmates due to their ability to communicate with them and understand their needs and feelings.

The results showed that the highest degree of emotional intelligence was the statement: "I prepare well before a mathematics lesson, so that I can teach students easily." This is due to the advance preparation that mathematics teachers do before starting the teaching process, and this helps them avoid any problems that arise during teaching, and teach students smoothly and easily.

As for the second level, the phrase: "I can provide answers to difficult mathematics questions." Prior preparation and effective mastery of mathematics make the mathematics teacher familiar with all the details of teaching mathematics, and he has the ability to answer students' questions, no matter how difficult they are. The results indicated that the mathematics teacher can easily evoke positive feelings such as fun and humor, and this helps to break the mathematics stagnation and makes learning mathematics acceptable and more feasible for students.

The Second question:

The results of the study indicated that the degree of job performance of mathematics teachers is high. This indicates that mathematics teachers work hard to provide a suitable climate for teaching mathematics, seek to achieve learning outcomes and help their colleagues in doing so, and seek to provide suggestions and recommendations that help the school administration organize work, with mathematics teachers being able to accept any additional work requested of them outside the framework of teaching. .

The Third question:

The results of the study indicated there is a statistically significant correlation the Possession of emotional intelligence among mathematics teachers and their job performance, where the value of the correlation between emotional intelligence and job performance reached (0.856). This indicates that the relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance is positive and strong. The higher the emotional intelligence of mathematics teachers, the greater their job performance, which reflects the improvement towards their job performance. The opposite is true, that is, the lower the emotional intelligence, the lower the job performance of mathematics teachers. This means that emotional intelligence has a significant role in improving job performance. This result differed from the study of Samir (2016), which indicated that the relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance is moderate.

CONCLUSIONS

The study reached a set of conclusions:

1. The degree the Possession of emotional intelligence mathematics teachers in Jordan is high.
2. The highest levels of emotional intelligence that mathematic teachers possess are:
 - a. I prepare well before the mathematics lesson, so that I can teach the students easily.
 - b. I can provide answers to difficult mathematics questions.
 - c. I can summon positive emotions such as fun and humor easily.
3. the relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance is positive and strong.

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